

Research Article

A Study to Assess the Level of Self Esteem among Persons with Alcoholism in a Selected Hospital at Bangalore

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Received: November 14, 2020 **Accepted:** December 14, 2020 **Published:** December 27, 2020

Abstract: Background: Self-esteem is an essential contribution to the life process and is indispensable to normal and healthy self-development, and has a value for survival (James). Self-esteem is the reflection of the understanding of oneself and sense of personal value. Self-esteem and addiction go hand in hand. Low self-esteem is considered the number one factor for causing a drug or alcohol addiction. Most people with the drug or alcohol addiction or people who are at risk for developing and addiction, have a low self-esteem. **Objectives:** (1) To assess the level of self-esteem among persons with alcoholism. (2). To determine the association of self-esteem with demographic variables of persons with alcoholism. **Methods:** Descriptive design was adopted to conduct a study on 60 alcoholic patient's admitted in psychiatric ward, gastroenterology ward at St. Johns Medical College Hospital, Bangalore. In the study subjects were selected using purposive sampling technique. Rosenberg Self Esteem scale was used to assess the self-esteem among the selected samples. The data analyzed using a descriptive and inferential statistics. **Result:** The findings of the study revealed that majority of the samples were in the age group of 36-55 which contributed to be 60%. Males were more than females that is 88.3% and 11.6% respectively. Most of the persons with alcoholism were married that is 85%. Alcoholics whose educational qualification was intermediate constituted of 71.67%. Unskilled workers contributed 75% of alcoholics. 81.6% of persons with alcoholism were Hindus, people with no family history of alcoholism contributed 56.6%. Among the beginners of alcoholism 12-24 year old people contributed 65%. 71.6% of people consume 100-300ml of alcohol. People who earned 5000-20000 contributed 71.6%. The age, education, occupation and family history of the alcoholic peoples have no associations with the self-esteem whereas the age of beginning of alcohol, quantity of consumption and income have association with self-esteem. **Conclusion:** The finding of the study showed that majority of the persons with alcoholism has normal self-esteem.

Keywords: Alcoholism, occupation, consumption.

Introduction

According to American Medical Association, "Alcoholism is an illness characterized by significant impairment that is directly associated with persistent and excessive use of alcohol. Impairment may involve physiological, psychological or social dysfunction". Psychologically speaking, alcoholism has less to do with "how much" someone is drinking, and more to do with what happens when they drink. The word alcohol comes from the Arabic word "al kohl" which means "the essence".^{1,2} According to World Health Organization report released its Global Status on alcoholism and Health. About 38.3 percent of the world's population is reported to consume alcohol regularly^{3,4}. On average

an individual consumption amounts to 6.2 litres of alcohol each year. The report only considers individuals over 15 years of age.

The report says that about 30 percent of India's population, just less than a third of the country's populace—consumed alcohol regularly. Some 11 percent are moderate to heavy drinkers. The average Indian consumes about 4.3 liters of alcohol per annum, says the report. The rural average is much higher at about 11.4 liters a year. According to an Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Report, Alcoholism increased by about 55 percent between 1992 and 2012. It is a quickly rising concern among the youth of the country.⁵

Self-esteem is the reflection of the understanding of oneself and sense of personal value. In fact it can be said that self-esteem is a general judgment about us. In addition, the Mental Health and Counseling Center of the Texas also reported that low self-esteem can lead to lack of development and /or tendency toward drugs or alcohol consumption.^{6,7,8}

When a person is challenged by one of these, they may not only feel a lack of self-esteem, but they may also feel a sense of anger, loneliness, and depression. A person may begin to have difficulty in communicating and have several social conflicts. These can cause even lowered self-esteem, and other problems. The person may turn to drugs or alcohol to escape their feelings and problems.^{6,9,10}

Objectives of the Study

- ✓ To assess the level of self-esteem among persons with alcoholism.
- ✓ To determine the association of self-esteem with demographic variables of persons with alcoholism.

Research Hypothesis

- ✓ **H₁**: There will be a significant change in self-esteem of the persons with alcoholism.

Methodology

Research Approach: Research approach used was quantitative approach.

Research Design: The research design for the study was descriptive design.

Research Setting: The setting of the study included psychiatric ward, gastroenterology ward and patients visiting outpatient department of St. Johns Medical College Hospital, Bangalore.

Population: Persons with alcoholism between the age group of 19 to 55 years admitted in psychiatry ward and gastroenterology ward and patients visiting outpatient department in St. John's Medical college Hospital, Bangalore.

Sample: The sample for the study was persons with alcoholism between the age group of 19-55 years admitted in Psychiatry ward and gastroenterology ward and patients visiting outpatient department of St. Johns Medical College Hospital, Bangalore and who met the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Sample Size: To observe the self-esteem level of persons with alcoholism with precision 5 % and confidence interval 95%, sample size selected for the main study was 60.

Sampling Technique: Purposive sampling technique was used in this study.

Criteria for Selection

Inclusion Criteria

- ✓ Persons with alcoholism, aged between 19 to 55 years.

- ✓ Persons with alcoholism who can read and understand Kannada or English.

Exclusion Criteria

- ✓ Alcoholic clients who are diagnosed with major psychiatric illness.

Instrument Used

Section A: Interview schedule to collect the demographic variables.

Section B: Rosenberg self-esteem scale was used to assess the level of self-esteem among persons with alcoholism.

Description of the instruments

Section A: Demographic Performa

In this study demographic variable of person with alcoholism refers to age, gender, education, occupation, marital status, socio-economic status, religion, family history of alcoholism and history of de-addiction.

Section B: Rosenberg self-esteem scale was used to assess the level of self-esteem among persons with alcoholism

Rosenberg self-esteem scale was used to assess the level of self-esteem among persons with alcoholism. The Rosenberg self-esteem scale is considered a reliable and valid quantitative tool for self-esteem assessment. It is a ten item likert-type scale with items answered on a four point scale- from strongly agrees to strongly disagree. Five of the items have positively worded statements and five have negatively worded ones.

Method of Data Collection

Ethical clearance to conduct this study was obtained from the institutional ethical committee, SJNAHS, Bangalore. A formal permission was obtained from administrative authorities of St. Johns Medical College Hospital. The study was conducted in psychiatry, gastroenterology. 60 subjects were selected using purposive sampling based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. The data collection period was from 05-03-2018 to 30-03-2018.

Subject information sheet was read to the subjects to understand the nature of study and written informed consent was obtained. Interview method was used to collect the data. The interview was conducted in one to one basis. Demographic Performa was used to collect the baseline variables. Rosenberg self-esteem scale was used to assess the self-esteem in persons with alcoholism. The subjects took a total time of 30 minutes to answer all the items in the tool.

Results

Section I: Description of demographic variables of persons with alcoholism

- ✓ The 60% of subjects are in age group 36-55years,
- ✓ The 88.3% are males, 85% are married,
- ✓ The 73.3% have completed intermediate education,
- ✓ The 75% are unskilled,
- ✓ The 81.6% belong to Hindu religion,
- ✓ The 56.7% had no family history of alcoholism,
- ✓ The 65% began consuming alcohol at the age 12-24years,
- ✓ The 71.7% consumed 100-300ml per day and
- ✓ The 71.7% had an income ranging 5000-20000.

Section II: Frequency distribution Mean, Median, Mean percentage, Standard Deviation to describe the level of self-esteem with persons with alcoholism.

Table 1. Description of self-esteem of persons with alcoholism, Mean, Median, Mean percentage, and Standard deviation (n=60)

Self-Esteem Maximum Score	Range	Mean	Mean %	Median	Standard Deviation
30	3-29	16.4	54.6	15.5	6.53

Table 1 reveals that the mean score of self-esteem of total alcoholic subjects was 16.4 with median 15.5 and SD 6.53.

Figure 1. Percentage distribution of level of self-esteem among persons with alcoholism

Section III: Description of association of self-esteem with selected demographic variables

There was a statistical significant association between self-esteem and selected demographic variable such as age of beginning of alcoholism, quantity of consumption of alcohol per day and income, whereas in other selected demographic variables such as in age, education, occupation and family history there is no association with the self-esteem.

Nursing Implications

In mental health team nurse play an important role in the provision of psychosocial therapy and holistic care which include physical, mental, social and spiritual comfort. It can be included as part of regular nursing intervention which includes counseling, group therapy, motivational interviewing, and supportive psychotherapy etc. to improve the self-esteem in alcoholic patients.

Nursing Practice

It deals with providing comprehensive care to individual regardless of their illness, background which includes economic status, religion and their education. Nurses should be aware about the impact of alcohol addiction in individual in order to give psycho education to the patient. Regular nursing intervention which includes counseling, group therapy, motivational interviewing, and supportive psychotherapy etc. To improve the self-esteem in alcoholic patients. Nurses should carry out an assessment of self-esteem in alcoholic patients to carry out the intervention.

Nursing Education

Alcohol and drug dependence is a growing problem and consequences of its cost heavily to the community and form a major health problem. The majority of the alcoholic persons do not enter

treatment due to lack of self-esteem. The nursing curriculum deals with providing holistic care to family and community. Nursing education should lay emphasis on preparing prospective nurse who are able to deal with psychological aspects of illness through communication and counselling.

Nursing Administration

Nursing administration can arrange in service education regarding alcoholism and its relation to self-esteem. Awareness programs can be conducted in clinical setting regarding elevation of self-esteem in patients. Nurse administrators should train the nurses to provide psycho education to patients to improve their self-esteem.

Nursing Research

Nursing research helps in providing evidence based practices, thus improving the quality of nursing care. Further research can be conducted to assess the reason behind alcoholic clients being with low self-esteem.

Limitations

- ✓ The duration of the data collection was limited to 2 weeks but due to lack of availability of samples data collection extended to 4 weeks
- ✓ Few samples were not cooperative to the study.
- ✓ Lack of communication between the research group members because of different duty timings.

Recommendations

- ✓ The same study can be conducted on a larger sample and at different settings which may yield reliable result and make generalization.
- ✓ Study to assess the self-esteem of alcoholics can be conducted in community setting.
- ✓ A qualitative study can be conducted to analyze the family structure of alcoholic persons with low self-esteem.
- ✓ Interventional study can be conducted to increase the self-esteem alcoholic persons.

Conclusion

- ✓ Majority of the samples were in the age group of 36-55 which contribute to be 60%.
- ✓ Alcoholic whose educational qualification is intermediate constitute of 71.67%.
- ✓ Unskilled workers contribute 75% of alcoholics.
- ✓ The study showed that majority of the persons with alcoholism has normal self-esteem.
- ✓ The age, education, occupation and family history of the alcoholic peoples have no associations with the self-esteem whereas the age of beginning of alcohol, quantity of consumption and income have association with self-esteem.

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

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Citation: Quadras J, Youtso N, Joseph N, Verghese N, Mathew N, Isaac P, Reenu S, Reena J. A Study to Assess the Level of Self Esteem among Persons with Alcoholism in a Selected Hospital at Bangalore. *Int J Rec Innov Med Clin Res.* 2020;2(4):153-158.

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